

Incentives and regulation in the Swiss healthcare system

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INTRODUCTORY CHAPTER

The Swiss healthcare system, widely renowned for its excellence, presents a complex landscape intertwined with various stakeholders and diverse incentives. These intricacies can pose challenges, potentially leading patients to make suboptimal choices when navigating through the healthcare system. On the basis of three selected research questions, this doctoral thesis aims to break down the complexities inherent in the Swiss healthcare system, providing patients with valuable insights for informed decision-making derived from a comprehensive data source while striving to enhance the quality of health service provision in pursuit of continual improvement within healthcare. For this research, we utilized insurance claims data provided by Helsana - one of the largest health insurances - ensuring unwavering commitment to preserving data protection of individuals. Regarding the statistical methods, in all three research studies the dataset was descriptively analyzed and regression analysis, tailored to the underlying dataset, was performed aiming to isolate the association of the target variable and variable of interest while maintaining the all the other variables constant. These combined methodologies allowed for a comprehensive breakdown of the complexity within healthcare provision, offering a detailed comprehension of the association among the variables under scrutiny.

The thesis is centered around patients and, therefore, all three studies used outcome variables at the patient level. Study 1 (chapter 1) and study 3 (chapter 3) focused specifically on medication prescriptions (opioids and biosimilars, respectively), whereas study 2 (chapter 2) focused on patient outcomes specifically in the hospital setting. Sociodemographic variables of patients were used in all regression models along other relevant variables in order to identify risk factors of patients regarding the outcome of interest. More specifically, study 1 delves into opioid prescriptions in the context of pain management post knee replacement surgery. Due to their questioned efficacy in comparison to other non-opioid analgesics and

their side effects, especially in the long-term use, the use of opioids has been criticized. The study showed that of all patients, 3'445 (37.8%) received opioids in the postoperative year with most patients receiving opioids in the first 10 postoperative weeks (n=2'881, 31.6%), a majority had short duration of opioid use (n=3'067, 89.0%) and 2'211 (65.0%) had high peak opioid dose levels. Increasing age (66–75 and >75 vs 18–65) was associated with decreased, whereas preoperative non-opioid analgesics and opioids were associated with higher risk for opioid prescriptions. The high opioid demand is unexpected; however, it is important that patients and prescribing physicians consider alternative treatment options and ensure that benefits outweigh potential risks in the individual medical situation. Study 2 explores the link between surgical volumes for abdominal cancer procedures and treatment outcomes. Colon resections were the most common procedures (n = 1'690), followed by rectal resections (n = 709). For rectal, colon and pancreatic resections, an increase in the mean number of interventions per hospital and a reduction of low volume hospitals could be observed over the years. For the relationship between hospital volume and outcomes, we did not observe a clear dose-response relationship, as no significantly better outcomes were observed in the higher-volume category than in the lower-volume category. As cantons are responsible for healthcare planning and provision, they should ensure and measure provision quality also considering other factors that might have an influence on service provision which could not be ascertained from the database, such as surgeon experience, presence of multidisciplinary teams, or existing infrastructure. Study 3 examines biosimilars' prescriptions at treatment initiation and their determinants, as well as biological therapy switches, as the cost-saving potential of biosimilars is still under-researched in Switzerland. Although biosimilars' market share was low (28.6%), the number of prescriptions has increased (from 1'016 in 2016 to 6'976 in 2021). Only, few patients with medication switches (n=1'492, 8.5%) were detected. Increased relative price difference (difference in the price of available biosimilars relative to price of

corresponding reference product) was associated with decreased probability of biosimilar prescriptions, whereas male sex, an increase of available imitator drugs on the market, larger packaging sizes, and prescriptions from specialists or physicians in outpatient settings were associated with increased biosimilar use. Even if there is a high cost-saving potential of biosimilars for the healthcare system, patients should engage with the prescribing physician to assess whether a switch to biosimilar therapy might be sensible in their individual medical situation.

In summary, chapters 1 and 3 emphasize active patient involvement in treatment discussions and advocate for physicians to integrate patient preferences, beliefs, along with the available evidence to optimize therapy choices. Chapter 2 underscores the need to measure service provision quality and promote transparency for patients. Together, all these chapters give patients insights that support them in informed decision-making across three different topics. At the same time, the findings inform policy decisions, aiming to optimize healthcare provision, more specifically the provision of optimal pain management after knee replacement, strengthening quality in service provision in hospitals and provision of biological medication.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AIC: Akaike information criterion

ATC: Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical

BIC: Bayesian information criterion

EU: European Union

FOPH: Federal Office of Public Health

FOS: Federal Office of Statistics

FP: follow-up prescriptions

GEE: generalized estimating equations

HSM: Highly Specialized Medicine

IQI: Inpatient Quality Indicators

IP: initial prescription

IRR: Incidence risk ratio

KR: Knee replacement

LMW heparins: low-molecular-weight heparins

MED: morphine equivalent dose

NOU: Non opioid user

OR: Odds ratio

OU: Opioid User

PCG: Pharmaceutical Cost Groups

RMSE: root-mean-square error

WHO: World Health Organization

CHAPTER 1:

Opioid prescriptions after knee replacement: a retrospective study of pathways and prognostic factors in the Swiss healthcare setting

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CHAPTER 2:

Does hospital volume affect outcomes after abdominal cancer surgery: An analysis of Swiss health insurance claims data

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CHAPTER 3:

Initial prescriptions and switches of biologicals: an analysis of prescription pathways and determinants

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